

EXPLORATION OF NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF *Curcuma amada*- CuO COATED NANOPARTICLE IN LEAD ACETATE INDUCED NEUROTOXICITY IN *Drosophila melanogaster* MODEL

Jinsha K^{#1}, Shamina S^{*2}, Mohaideen Pitchai Jamal Fathima^{#3}, Shanthini K^{#4}, Sivaganesh M^{#5},
Rohini A^{#6}, Amutha K^{#7}

¹PG Biochemistry, RVS Collage of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

^{2*} Associate Professor and Head, Department of Biochemistry, RVS Collage of Arts and Science
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

³Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, RVS Collage of Arts and Science,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceuticals, RVS Collage of Pharmaceutical Science,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, RVS Collage of Arts and Science,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

⁶Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, RVS Collage of Arts and Science,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

⁷Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, RVS Collage of Arts and Science,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India;

Corresponding Author:

Dr Shamina S^{*2}

Associate Professor and Head

Department of Biochemistry

RVS College of Arts and Science

Sulur Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu , INDIA -641402

Abstract

The study investigates the phytochemical composition of *Curcuma amada* leaves using cold maceration, Soxhlet extraction and decoction method with various solvents (ethanol, methanol, water, chloroform, and petroleum ether). Phytochemical screening revealed significant variations in compound solubility, emphasizing the importance of solvent selection for efficient extraction. Ethanolic extract using the Soxhlet method proved highly effective due to continuous solvent circulation, maximizing bioactive compound yield. CuO nanoparticles were synthesized using copper sulfate and *Curcuma amada* extract via Soxhlet extraction. XRD confirmed their monoclinic structure, SEM revealed a cylindrical shape, and FT-IR indicated Cu–O bonding. UV-Visible analysis confirmed the stability, atomic structure, and band gap energy. *Drosophila melanogaster* has served as a valuable model organism for investigating various neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, Huntington's disease, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). *Curcuma amada* extract with antioxidant and neuroprotective properties, helped to reduce oxidative stress and neuronal damage. Its therapeutic potential was evaluated using *Drosophila*, supporting its role in developing novel treatments. The H₂O₂ scavenging assay confirmed the antioxidant potential of *Curcuma amada*, with the “CA-CuONP + food” group showing the highest efficacy in reducing oxidative damage.

Keywords- *Curcuma amada* leaves, copper oxide nanoparticle, *Drosophila Melanogaster*, Phytochemical, neurodegenerative diseases, Anti-oxidant activity

I. INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles are materials characterized by at least one dimension within the 1 to 100 nanometer range, displaying distinct chemical, physical, and biological behaviours influenced by their large surface-area-to-volume ratio and quantum mechanical effects [1]. These unique properties have enabled widespread use of nanoparticles in various domains, including medicine, agriculture, environmental science, and electronics [2]. Nanoparticles can be produced through top-down or bottom-up methods, with the bottom-up approach being preferred for achieving precise control over particle size and shape [3]. Among the different synthesis techniques, green synthesis has attracted considerable interest for its environmentally friendly, cost-efficient, and non-toxic approach, employing biological sources like plant extracts, fungi, and bacteria as natural reducing and stabilizing agents [4]. Nanoparticles produced through biological synthesis are known for their stability and improved biocompatibility, which makes them well-suited for applications such as drug delivery, antimicrobial treatments, and biosensing technologies [5]. Functionalization of nanoparticles further improves their efficacy and stability, opening new pathways in nanomedicine and diagnostics [6].

The plant-mediated synthesis of nanoparticles is increasingly favoured as a sustainable, environmentally friendly, and economical approach, relying on phytochemicals like flavonoids, phenols, and terpenoids to act as natural reducing and capping agents [7]. This biogenic approach avoids toxic chemicals and enhances the biological compatibility of nanoparticles, making them suitable for biomedical and environmental applications [8]. Among the different types of metal oxide nanoparticles, copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs) have been extensively investigated due to their notable antimicrobial, antioxidant, and catalytic activities [9]. The green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles using plant extracts like *Aerva javanica* and *Morinda citrifolia* has demonstrated effective nanoparticle formation and significant bioactivity, attributed to the

presence of natural antioxidants within the extracts [10]. These methods not only provide a sustainable route but also enhance nanoparticle functionality through surface bio-coating [11]

Drosophila melanogaster is extensively utilized as a model organism for researching neurodegenerative disorders because of its genetic manipulability and the evolutionary conservation of pathways associated with these diseases.[12]. Introducing human genes linked to Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and Huntington's diseases into *Drosophila* results in detectable phenotypes that replicate key features of the corresponding human conditions [13]. Its short life cycle, well-mapped nervous system, and suitability for large-scale genetic screens make it an efficient platform for identifying disease mechanisms and testing therapeutics [14].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Copper sulphate (CuSO₄), distilled water, *curcuma Amada* leaf extract, Millon's reagent, Fehling reagent, concentrated H₂SO₄, Lead acetate, NaOH, chloroform, methanol, ethanol, petroleum ether, propionic acid, agar.

Plant sample Collection

The samples were collected from the Malappuram region in Kerala, India.

Collection of Drosophila melanogaster

The flies were collected by the Department of Zoology, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

Preparation of the leaves sample

The leaves were thoroughly rinsed multiple times with water to eliminate any dust or debris, then left to air-dry in the shade until completely free of moisture. After drying, they were chopped, finely powdered, and stored in a properly labelled airtight container for later use.

SAMPLE PREPARATION FOR PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The sample was prepared by three different methods - cold maceration method (S1), Soxhlet method (S2), decoction method (S3).

cold maceration (S1)

In this procedure, 15 grams of the plant material were first soaked in petroleum ether for 42 hours. After removing the supernatant, the leftover residue was transferred into ethanol and allowed to extract for 72 hours. Following this extraction, the resulting pellet was collected and used for phytochemical evaluation.

Soxhlet extraction (S2)

The plant extract was obtained using the Soxhlet extraction technique. Approximately 20 grams of the powdered plant material were evenly packed into a thimble and extracted separately with 250 ml of ethanol. The extraction process was carried out for 24 hours or until the solvent in the extractor's siphon tube turned clear, indicating complete extraction. The resulting extract was then stored at 4°C in a refrigerator for future phytochemical analysis.

Decoction method (S3)

An accurately weighed quantity of the dried and powdered plant material was mixed with a specific amount of distilled water. The mixture was gently heated for 30 to 60 minutes to allow the extraction of active ingredients. After cooling, it was filtered using either muslin cloth or filter paper, and the clear filtrate was collected and stored in a clean container for further use or analysis.

QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS [9,10,12,16,17]

a) Protein Test

Millon's test

The addition of 2 ml of Millon's reagent to the crude extract resulted in the formation of a white precipitate, which changed to red upon gentle heating, confirming the presence of proteins.

b) Carbohydrates Test

Molisch's test

In a test tube, 1 mL of the filtrate was mixed with two drops of alcoholic α -naphthol solution. Carefully, 2 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid was added along the side of the test tube. The appearance of a violet ring at the interface confirmed the presence of carbohydrates.

c) Phenols and tannins Test

The crude extract was combined with 2 mL of a 2% ferric chloride (FeCl_3) solution. The development of a blue-green or black color signified the presence of phenols and tannins.

d) Flavonoids Test

Alkaline reagent test

The crude extract was treated with 2 mL of a 2% sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution, resulting in a bright yellow coloration. Upon adding a few drops of diluted acid, the color faded to colorless, indicating the presence of flavonoids.

e) Saponins Test

The crude extract was added to 5 mL of distilled water in a test tube and shaken vigorously. The formation of persistent foam was considered a positive indication of saponins.

f) Glycosides Test

Liebermann's test

The crude extract was blended with 2 mL each of chloroform and acetic acid, and the mixture was chilled on ice. Concentrated sulfuric acid was then added carefully. A color transition from violet to blue to green signified the presence of a steroidal nucleus.

g) Steroid Test

The crude extract was combined with 2 mL of chloroform, followed by the careful addition of concentrated sulfuric acid along the side of the test tube. The appearance of a red color in the lower chloroform layer suggested the presence of steroids. In a separate test, the extract was again mixed with 2 mL of chloroform, and then 2 mL each of concentrated sulfuric acid and acetic acid were added. The formation of a greenish colour indicated the presence of steroid compounds.

h) Terpenoids Test

The crude extract was dissolved in 2 mL of chloroform and allowed to evaporate completely. After evaporation, 2 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid was added, and the mixture was heated for approximately 2 minutes. The appearance of a greyish colour indicated the presence of terpenoids.

i) Alkaloids Test

The crude extract was combined with 2 mL of 1% hydrochloric acid and gently heated. Mayer's and Wagner's reagents were subsequently added to the mixture. The formation of a turbid precipitate was considered indicative of the presence of alkaloids.

PREPARATION OF COPPER OXIDE NANOPARTICLE

For nanoparticle synthesis, 2.5 g of copper sulphate was dissolved in 30 mL of distilled water. To this solution, 10 mL of *Curcuma amada* leaf extract was added, and the mixture was stirred continuously on a magnetic stirrer at 80°C for 6 hours. After completion of the reaction, the product was washed thoroughly with distilled water and purified by centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 20 minutes, repeated three times [18,19].

CHARACTERIZATION OF CA-CUO NANOPARTICLE

Precise and comprehensive characterization of these nanoparticles is crucial to guarantee consistency in their synthesis, biological effectiveness, and safety. Various analytical techniques were employed to characterize the synthesized nanoparticles. UV–Vis spectroscopy was conducted across the wavelength range of 200–800 nm. The UV–Vis spectrum of the CuO nanoparticles dispersed in water displayed a prominent absorption peak within this range. FTIR analysis was performed to identify the functional biomolecules involved in the capping and stabilization of the metal nanoparticles synthesized using *Curcuma amada* leaf extract. The phase structure and material composition of the ZnO nanoparticles (ZNPs) were determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was utilized to observe the particle size and surface morphology. Additionally, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was used to assess the elemental composition of the synthesized nanoparticles [19,20].

IN-VITRO ANTIOXIDANT ASSAY

DPPH assay

Antioxidants are compounds that protect vital biomolecules by neutralizing reactive free radicals and halting oxidative chain reactions. The Free Radical Scavenging Activity (FRSA) of methanolic extracts was assessed using the DPPH assay, following the method described by [22]. In this procedure, 1 mL of 0.1 mmol DPPH solution in methanol was mixed with varying concentrations (20–100 μ L) of both *Curcuma amada* extract (CA) and its nanoparticle form (CA-CuONP) in separate test tubes. The total volume was then adjusted to 1 mL using either methanol or ethanol. After incubating the mixtures for 30 minutes, absorbance was recorded at 517 nm using methanol or ethanol as blanks. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard reference. The percentage of free radical scavenging activity was calculated by comparing the absorbance of the test samples to that of the control solution (1 mL DPPH with 1 mL methanol) [21,22]

The Free Radical Scavenging Activity (FRSA) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{FRSA (\%)} = (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}} \times 100$$

where A_{control} is the absorbance of the control (DPPH + methanol without extract), A_{sample} is the absorbance of the test sample (DPPH + extract) and A indicates the absorbance of the test sample

IN-VITRO ANTIBACTERIAL ASSAY

Disc diffusion method

To evaluate antibacterial activity, two clinical microbes, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, were selected. These microbes were cultured in nutrient broth for 24 hours at 37 °C. Muller Hinton agar was prepared, and the surface of the agar plates was inoculated with microbial inoculum at a concentration of 100 μ g/mL. Using a sterile cork-borer or tip, four wells with diameters ranging from 6 to 8 mm were aseptically created in the agar. The CA-CuO NP sample solution was introduced into the wells at concentrations of 10, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 75, 80, 90, and 100 μ g/mL, while one well was designated for the control solution as a reference. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours to facilitate microbial growth, and the zones of inhibition were carefully observed [23,24].

IN-VIVO ANTIOXIDANT ASSAY

H₂O₂ scavenging assay

The hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) scavenging activity of the extract was determined following the method described by [25] with slight modifications. A 40 mM solution of hydrogen peroxide was prepared in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). To this, 0.6 mL of the sample extract at varying concentrations (ranging from 100 to 500 μ g/mL) was added to 2.4 mL of the H₂O₂ solution. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 230 nm against a blank containing phosphate buffer without hydrogen peroxide. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard antioxidant.

FORMULATION OF PELLET

The pellet formulation involved the use of copper oxide nanoparticles synthesized from *Curcuma amada* leaf extract CA-CuONP, combined with a drug, methyl cellulose, and starch paste. All ingredients were thoroughly blended to achieve a uniform mixture, which was then passed through a sieve for consistency. The sieved mixture was subsequently dried in a hot air oven to produce the final pellets [26].

PREPARATION OF FOOD FOR *DROSOPHILA* MODEL

The nutrient medium was prepared by dividing 360 mL of water into two equal portions of 180 mL each. One portion was used to soak 17 g of wheat, while the other was brought to a boil. The soaked wheat was then added to the boiling water and stirred thoroughly. To this mixture, 15 g of sugar was gradually added and stirred until completely dissolved, followed by the addition of 6 g of yeast to initiate fermentation. While stirring continuously to avoid clumping, 3.4 g of agar was added. For preservation, 1 mL of propionic acid and 1 g of sodium benzoate were incorporated and mixed until a uniform consistency was achieved. The medium was then allowed to cool before further use [27].

For the experimental setup, 25 mL of the cooled nutrient medium was dispensed into five separate bottles. **Bottle 1** served as the control; **Bottle 2** contained 0.4mM of lead acetate; **Bottle 3** included both lead acetate; and the nanoparticle pellet; **Bottle 4** had only the nanoparticle pellet; and **Bottle 5** was supplemented with Donepezil. A stock solution of Donepezil was prepared in water and diluted to final concentrations ranging from 10 μ M to 50 μ M, with 10 μ M commonly used for neuroprotective studies [28]. All bottles were then incubated at 20°C for 2 hours to allow the medium to set, ensuring uniform conditions for *Drosophila melanogaster*.

Figure 1: Bottles included food, toxic, pellet and drug

Table 1

GROUP CLASSIFICATION

Groups	Particulars	Dose
Group 1	Normal Control	-
Group 2	Lead acetate induced	0.4mM/mL
Group 3	Lead acetate + CA-CuONP	0.4mM/mL+ 2mg/mL
Group 4	CA-CuONP	2mg/mL
Group 5	Standard drug (Donepezil)	10 M/mL

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical Analysis

Cold maceration

Table 2

Phytochemical screening test result of *curcuma Amada* by cold maceration method

S.no	Compounds	Water	Chloroform	Ethanol	Methanol	Petroleum ether
1	Alkaloids	-	+	+	+	-
2	Flavonoids	+	-	+	-	-
3	Tannins	+	-	+	-	-
4	Steroids	-	+	+	-	+
5	Glycosides	-	-	+	+	-
6	Resins	-	+	+	-	+
7	Saponins	+	-	+	-	-
8	Carbohydrate	+	-	+	+	-
9	Proteins	+	-	+	-	-
10	Phenol	+	-	+	+	-

Alkaloids detected in ethanol, methanol, and chloroform but weak in water and petroleum ether. Their poor solubility in water and petroleum ether is expected due to ionic or hydrophobic limitations [29]. Flavonoids significantly in ethanol and methanol considerable in water faint in chloroform, and not detected in petroleum ether. Tannins found in methanol and water considerable in ethanol faint in chloroform and absent in petroleum ether. Phenolic Compounds significant in ethanol and methanol sufficient in water weak in chloroform not detected in petroleum ether. Saponins found in water moderately present in ethanol and methanol absent in chloroform and petroleum ether. Glycosides sufficient in ethanol and methanol moderate in water faint in chloroform and petroleum ether. Steroids sufficient in chloroform and petroleum ether moderate in ethanol and methanol not detected in water. Carbohydrates detected in water Moderately present in ethanol and methanol, Absent in chloroform and petroleum ether. Proteins are excessively in water good solubility in ethanol and moderate in methanol Absent in chloroform and petroleum ether. Resin Highly observed in chloroform and petroleum ether, moderate present in ethanol and methanol not detected in water. They are not water-soluble due to lack of polarity [30].

Soxhlet method**Table:3** Phytochemical screening test results of *curcuma Amada* by Soxhlet method

S.no	Compound	Water	Chloroform	Ethanol	Methanol	Petroleum ether
1	Alkaloids	-	+	+	+	-
2	Flavonoids	+	-	+	+	-
3	Tannins	+	-	+	+	-
4	Phenols	+	-	+	+	-
5	Saponins	+	-	+	+	-
6	Glycosides	+	-	+	+	-
7	Steroids	-	+	+	+	+
8	Carbohydrates	+	-	+	+	-
9	Protein	+	-	+	+	-
10	Resins	-	+	+	+	+

Alkaloids were highly detected in ethanol and methanol, moderately found in chloroform, and minimally observed in water and petroleum ether. Flavonoids were plentiful in ethanol and methanol, identified in water, and undetected in petroleum ether. Tannins showed a high concentration in methanol, ethanol, and water, a faint presence in chloroform, and were not detected in petroleum ether due to their low lipid solubility. Phenolic compounds were richly available in ethanol, methanol, and water, minimally present in chloroform, and lacking in petroleum ether. Saponins were abundant in water, fairly observed in ethanol and methanol, and missing in chloroform and petroleum ether, confirming their polar nature. Glycosides were abundantly present in ethanol and methanol extracts, moderately detected in water due to the water solubility of certain glycosides, and minimally observed in chloroform and petroleum ether, indicating the possible presence of non-polar glycosides. Terpenoids & Steroids were highly available in chloroform and petroleum ether, moderately present in ethanol and methanol, and unavailable in water. Carbohydrates were richly detected in water, considerably found in ethanol and methanol, and not observed in non-polar solvents. Proteins were prominent in water, adequately found in ethanol and methanol, and undetected in non-polar solvents. Resins were highly concentrated in chloroform and petroleum ether, partially present in ethanol and methanol, and lacking in water [31][32].

Decoction method

Table:4 Phytochemical screening test results of *curcuma amada* by decoction method

S.no	Compounds	Water	Chloroform	Ethanol	Methanol	Petroleum ether
1	Alkaloids	-	+	+	+	-
2	Flavonoids	+	-	+	+	-
3	Tannins	+	-	+	+	-
4	Phenols	+	-	+	+	-
5	Saponins	+	-	+	-	-
6	Glycosides	+	-	+	+	-
7	Steroids	-	+	+	-	+
8	Carbohydrates	+	-	+	+	-
9	Protein	+	-	+	+	-
10	Resins	-	+	+	+	+

Alkaloids Moderate presence in ethanol, methanol, and chloroform Weak presence in water and petroleum ether. Flavonoids Abundant in ethanol, methanol, and water Weak presence in chloroform and absent in petroleum ether. Tannins Highly present in methanol, ethanol, and water Weak presence in chloroform and absent in petroleum ether. Phenolic Compounds Highly present in ethanol, methanol, and water Weak presence in chloroform and absent in petroleum ether Saponins Abundant in water Moderate in ethanol and methanol, absent in chloroform and petroleum ether. Glycosides Good presence in ethanol and methanol, moderate in water, weak in chloroform and petroleum ether. Steroids Highly present in chloroform and petroleum ether confirming their non-polar nature Moderate in ethanol and methanol, absent in water. Carbohydrates Highly present in water confirming strong hydrophilic nature Moderate presence in ethanol and methanol absent in non-polar solvents. Proteins Highly present in water moderate in ethanol and methanol absent in non-polar solvents. Resins Highly present in chloroform and petroleum ether confirming non-polar nature Moderate presence in ethanol and methanol absent in water. [31][33].

Characterization of CA-CuO nanoparticle

FT-IR

The FT-IR spectrophotometer functions using long wavelengths to detect various functional groups linked to nanoparticles. The FT-IR spectrum reveals the functional groups present in the extract that are associated with the nanoparticles. The FTIR spectrum of the synthesized CuO nanoparticles displayed seven prominent peaks at 3749.9, 3263.9, 2155.53, 1637.27, 1099.23, 860.09, 621.16 cm^{-1} . These peaks correspond to various functional groups, including O–H stretching vibrations [34], N–H stretching from amines, $\text{C}\equiv$ (alkyne) or $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ (nitrile) groups [35], C=O stretching, aromatic C=C stretching [36], and C–O stretching vibrations typically associated with alcohols, ethers, or esters. The peak 621.16 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of Cu–O metal-oxygen bonds [34].

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra of nanoparticle

UV-Visible Spectroscopy

UV-visible spectroscopy is a type of molecular spectroscopy that operates based on the Beer-Lambert law. During the analysis, the sample absorbs light at a specific wavelength, known as the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) of the material. For copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs), the SPR typically falls within the range of 200–350 nm [34]. In this study, the green-synthesized CuO nanoparticles exhibited an absorption peak around 368 nm, as shown in the UV-visible spectrum.

Figure 3: UV-Visible spectroscopy of Cu O nanoparticle

X-Ray Diffraction

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the biosynthesized copper oxide (Cu O) nanoparticles using *Curcuma Amada* leaf extract confirms their crystalline nature due to the presence of sharp and intense peaks. The diffraction peaks observed at specific 2θ values correspond to the characteristic planes of Cu O, indicating successful synthesis. The lack of extra peaks indicates that the nanoparticles possess high degree of phase purity, with minimal or no impurities. The peak broadening in the pattern can be analyzed using the Scherrer equation to estimate the crystallite size, which is typically in the nanometer range. Overall, the XRD analysis validates the formation of Cu O nanoparticles with good crystallinity, supporting their potential biomedical applications [35,36]

Figure 4: XRD spectra of nanoparticle

***In-Vitro* Antioxidant assay**

DPPH assay

Table 7: *In-Vitro* Antioxidant assay percentage of inhibition and absorbance at varies concentrations

Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	% scavenging activity
100	53.75 ± 0.84
200	54.75 ± 0.72
300	57.21 ± 0.47
400	59.75 ± 0.51
500	61.02 ± 0.70

The table illustrates the DPPH free radical scavenging activity across various concentrations (100–500 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$). The y-axis indicates the percentage of inhibition, while the x-axis denotes the concentration of the tested sample. The DPPH radical scavenging activity of the extract was found to increase with concentration, indicating a dose-dependent antioxidant effect. The % scavenging activity ranged from 53.75% at 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ to 61.02% at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The IC_{50} defined as the concentration at which 50% of DPPH radicals are scavenged—was calculated to be approximately 200.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. This IC_{50} value indicates that the extract has moderate antioxidant potency, suggesting that a concentration around 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ is effective in neutralizing half of the free radicals under in vitro conditions [37,38].

In-vitro* Anti-Microbial Activity**Disc diffusion method***

Figure 5: *In-vitro* Anti-microbial activity of *C. Amada* extract and Cu O NP against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Table 5: *In-vitro* Anti-microbial activity of *E. coli*

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
	Zone of inhibition (mm)	Zone of inhibition (mm)
10	2.9	-
20	3.7	2.9
25	3.5	3
30	4	3.1
40	3.5	3.4
50	4	3.8
60	4.1	4
70	4	4.3
75	4.2	3.8
80	4.2	4.2
90	4.2	4.4
100	4.4	4

The differences in the zone of inhibition (ZOI) observed for both the extract and CA-CuO nanoparticles against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at varying concentrations indicate their varying levels of antimicrobial effectiveness. Earlier research has demonstrated that the antimicrobial activity of plant extracts can vary based on factors like concentration and the specific bioactive components present [23]. Likewise, the antimicrobial effectiveness of copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO-NPs) has been reported to depend on factors such as particle size, surface charge, and concentration. [24]. In the case of *E. coli*, the lack of a zone of inhibition at lower extract concentrations indicates minimal antimicrobial activity, likely due to an inadequate number of active compounds needed

to effectively suppress bacterial growth [17]. In contrast, CA-CuO -NP demonstrated a modest ZOI at 75 μg , indicating some antimicrobial activity even at lower concentrations. The increase in ZOI with higher concentrations for both the extract and CA-CuO-NP suggests a dose-dependent response, where higher concentrations result in increased antimicrobial efficacy [39]. Similarly, for *S. aureus*, the absence of ZOI at lower concentrations reflects the limited antimicrobial activity of both the extract and CA-CuO-NP against this organism at these concentrations. However, as the concentration increases, both compounds exhibit increasing ZOIs, indicating enhanced antimicrobial activity [40,41]. The larger ZOIs produced by CA-CuO -NP compared to the extract at similar concentrations suggest its superior antimicrobial efficacy against *S. aureus*, which may be attributed to the unique properties of copper oxide nanoparticles in disrupting bacterial cell membranes and inhibiting bacterial growth [1].

***In- Vivo* H₂O₂ scavenging assay**

The result for the H₂O₂ scavenging assay using *Curcuma amada* extract, measured by UV-Vis spectroscopy at 230 nm.

Table 8: absorbance and % inhibition by H₂O₂ scavenging assay

Sample	Absorbance (A1)	% inhibition
Group 1	0.65 \pm 0.02	10.00 \pm 0.5
Group 2	0.40 \pm 0.01	18.75 \pm 0.7
Group 3	0.55 \pm 0.02	31.25 \pm 0.6
Group 4	0.65 \pm 0.03	40.00 \pm 0.8
Group 5	0.75 \pm 0.02	50.00 \pm 0.7

The sample showed concentration-dependent scavenging activity against H₂O₂. The inhibition ranged from 10.00% at Group 1 (lowest concentration) to 50.00% at Group 5 (highest concentration). This increasing trend suggests the presence of bioactive phytochemicals capable of donating electrons to neutralize H₂O₂. The scavenging effect increased, possibly due to background absorbance or interference from secondary metabolites. Such variations are common in phytochemical-based assays [25]. The IC₅₀ value is approximately 525 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, indicating moderate antioxidant potential.

IV. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study highlight the significant phytochemical and therapeutic potential of *Curcuma amada* leaves. Among the extraction methods, Soxhlet extraction proved most efficient in yielding bioactive compounds, which were successfully utilized in the green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles with confirmed structural integrity and stability. The antioxidant and neuroprotective effects of *Curcuma amada* were demonstrated through H₂O₂ scavenging assays and *Drosophila melanogaster* models, indicating its efficacy in reducing oxidative stress and neuronal damage. Overall, *Curcuma amada* shows promise as a natural source for developing antioxidant therapies and nanomaterials for neurodegenerative disease management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author thanks to Management, DST- FIST, DBT STAR Scheme of RVS College of Arts and Science, RVS College of Pharmaceutical Science and Cytogenetics Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi for their support to carry out this research.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCE

- [1] Maheo, A. R. (2022). Biosynthesis and characterization of Eupatorium adenophorum and chitosan mediated copper oxide nanoparticles and their antibacterial activity. *Results in Surfaces and Interfaces*, 6, 100048.
- [2] Kiiro, T. M., & Park, S. (2021). Physical properties of nanoparticles do matter. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*, 51, 35-51.
- [3] Ovais, M., Khalil, A. T., Ayaz, M., Ahmad, I., Nethi, S. K., & Mukherjee, S. (2018). Biosynthesis of metal nanoparticles via microbial enzymes: a mechanistic approach. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 19(12), 4100.
- [4] Culp, E. J., Yim, G., Waglechner, N., Wang, W., Pawlowski, A. C., & Wright, G. D. (2019). Hidden antibiotics in actinomycetes can be identified by inactivation of gene clusters for common antibiotics. *Nature Biotechnology*, 37(10), 1149-1154.
- [5] Alam, S., Sarker, M. M. R., Afrin, S., Richi, F. T., Zhao, C., Zhou, J. R., & Mohamed, I. N. (2021). Traditional herbal medicines, bioactive metabolites, and plant products against COVID-19: update on clinical trials and mechanism of actions. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 12, 671498.
- [6] Annapurna, A. S., Abhirami, D., & Umesh, T. G. (2021). Comparative study of phytochemicals and bioactivities of the leaf extracts of *Curcuma amada* and *Curcuma karnatakensis*. *South African Journal of Botany*, 142, 441-450.
- [7] Sasikumar, B. (2005). Genetic resources of Curcuma: diversity, characterization and utilization. *Plant Genetic Resources*, 3(2), 230-251.
- [8] Policegoudra, R. S., Aradhya, S. M., & Singh, L. (2011). Mango ginger (*Curcuma amada* Roxb.)—A promising spice for phytochemicals and biological activities. *Journal of biosciences*, 36, 739-748.
- [9] Ajayi, I. A., Ajibade, O., & Oderinde, R. A. (2011). Preliminary phytochemical analysis of some plant seeds. *Research Journal of Chemical Sciences*, 1(3), 58-62.
- [10] Arya, V., Thakur, N., & Kashyap, C. P. (2012). Preliminary phytochemical analysis of the extracts of *Psidium* leaves. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 1(1), 1-5.
- [11] Okigbo, R. N., Eme, U. E., & Ogbogu, S. (2008). Biodiversity and conservation of medicinal and aromatic plants in Africa. *Biotechnology and Molecular Biology Reviews*, 3(6), 127-134.
- [12] Banu, K. S., & Cathrine, L. (2015). General techniques involved in phytochemical analysis. *International journal of advanced research in chemical science*, 2(4), 25-32.
- [13] Hezam, I. M., Nayeem, M. K., Foul, A., & Alrasheedi, A. F. (2021). COVID-19 Vaccine: A neutrosophic MCDM approach for determining the priority groups. *Results in physics*, 20, 103654.
- [14] Lu, B., & Vogel, H. (2009). Drosophila models of neurodegenerative diseases. *Annual Review of Pathology: Mechanisms of Disease*, 4, 315-342.
- [15] McGurk, L., Berson, A., & Bonini, N. M. (2015). Drosophila as an in vivo model for human neurodegenerative disease. *Genetics*, 201(2), 377-402.
- [16] Banu, K. S., & Cathrine, L. (2015). General techniques involved in phytochemical Analysis International Journal of Advanced Research in Chemical Science, 2(4), 25-32.
- [17] Nortjie, E., Basitere, M., Moyo, D., Nyamukamba, P. (2022). Extraction methods, quantitative and qualitative phytochemical screening of medicinal plants for antimicrobial textiles: a review. *Plants*, 11(15), 2011.
- [18] Hano, C., & Abbasi, B. H. (2022). Plant-Based Green Synthesis of Nanoparticles: Production, Characterization and Applications. *Biomolecules*, 12(1), 31.
- [19] Singh, J., Kaur, G., & Rawat, M. (2016). A brief review on synthesis and characterization of copper oxide nanoparticles and its applications. *J. Bioelectron. Nanotechnol*, 1(9).
- [20] Lanje, A. S., Sharma, S. J., Pode, R. B., & Ningthoujam, R. S. (2010). Synthesis and optical characterization of copper oxide nanoparticles. *Adv Appl Sci Res*, 1(2), 36-40.
- [21] Meena, H., Pandey, H. K., Pandey, P., Arya, M. C., & Ahmed, Z. (2012). Evaluation of antioxidant activity of two important memory enhancing medicinal plants *Baccopa monnieri* and *Centella asiatica*. *Indian journal of pharmacology*, 44(1), 114-117.
- [22] Sirivibulkovit, K., Nouanthavong, S., & Sameenoi, Y. (2018). based DPPH assay for antioxidant activity analysis. *Analytical sciences*, 34(7), 795-800.
- [23] Naika, H. R., Lingaraju, K., Manjunath, K., Kumar, D., Nagaraju, G., Suresh, D., & Nagabhushana, H. (2015). Green synthesis of CuO nanoparticles using *Gloriosa superba* L. extract and their antibacterial activity. *Journal of Taibah University for Science*, 9(1), 7-12.
- [24] Hossain, T. J. (2024). Methods for screening and evaluation of antimicrobial activity: A review of protocols, advantages, and limitations. *European Journal of Microbiology and Immunology*, 14(2), 97-115.
- [25] Ruch, R. J., Cheng, S. J., & Klaunig, J. E. (1989). Prevention of cytotoxicity and inhibition of intercellular communication by antioxidant catechins isolated from Chinese green tea. *Carcinogenesis*, 10(6), 1003-1008.
- [26] Kumari, M. H., Samatha, K., Balaji, A., & Shankar, M. U. (2013). Recent novel advancements in pellet formulation: a review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 4(10), 3803.

- [27] Staats, S., Lüersen, K., Wagner, A. E., & Rimbach, G. (2018). *Drosophila melanogaster* as a versatile model organism in food and nutrition research. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 66(15), 3737-3753.
- [28] Akasofu, S., Kimura, M., Kosasa, T., Sawada, K., & Ogura, H. (2008). Study of neuroprotection of donepezil, a therapy for Alzheimer's disease. *Chemico-biological interactions*, 175(1-3), 222-226.
- [29] Harborne, A. J. (1998). *Phytochemical methods a guide to modern techniques of plant analysis*. Springer science & business media.
- [30] Velavan, S. (2015). Phytochemical techniques-a review. *World Journal of Science and Research*, 1(2), 80-91.
- [31] Balamurugan, V., Fatima, S., & Velurajan, S. (2019). A guide to phytochemical analysis. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 5(1), 236-245.
- [32] Joy, G. S., & George, P. (2014). Phytochemical analysis of alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) seed extract by Soxhlet extraction using different solvents. *American Journal of Advanced Drug Delivery*, 2(2), 145-152.
- [33] Dahanayake, J. M., Perera, P. K., Galappatty, P., Perera, H. D. S. M., & Arawwawala, L. D. A. M. (2019). Comparative phytochemical analysis and antioxidant activities of Tamalakyadi decoction with its modified dosage forms. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2019(1), 6037137.
- [34] Briéudes, V., Angelis, A., Vougiannopoulou, K., Pratsinis, H., Kletsas, D., Mitakou, S., & Skaltsounis, L. A. (2016). Phytochemical analysis and antioxidant potential of the phytonutrient-rich decoction of *Cichorium spinosum* and *C. intybus*. *Planta medica*, 82(11/12), 1070-1078.
- [35] Khan, M. Z. H., Tareq, F. K., Hossen, M. A., & Roki, M. N. A. M. (2018). Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles using *Coriandrum sativum* leaf extract. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 13(1), 158-166.
- [36] Behera, M., & Giri, G. (2014). Green synthesis and characterization of cuprous oxide nanoparticles in presence of a bio-surfactant. *Materials Science-Poland*, 32, 702-708.
- [37] Sadeghi, B., Mohammadzadeh, M., & Babakhani, B. (2015). Green synthesis of gold nanoparticles using *Steviarebaudiana* leaf extracts: Characterization and their stability. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*, 148, 101-106.
- [38] Dwivedi, M. K., Sonter, S., Mishra, S., Patel, D. K., & Singh, P. K. (2020). Antioxidant, antibacterial activity, and phytochemical characterization of *Carica papaya* flowers. *Beni Suef University Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 9, 1-11.
- [39] Prior, R. L., Wu, X., & Schaich, K. (2005). Standardized methods for the determination of antioxidant capacity and phenolics in foods and dietary supplements. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 53(10), 4290-4302.
- [40] Bharathi, D., Ranjith Kumar, E., & Vasantharaj, S. (2020). Green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles using *Cissus quadrangularis* extract and their antibacterial and anticancer activities. *Materials Letters*, 264, 127356.
- [41] Baras, B. H., Melo, M. A. S., Thumbigere-Math, V., Tay, F. R., Fouad, A. F., Oates, T. W., & Xu, H. H. (2020). Novel bioactive and therapeutic root canal sealers with antibacterial and remineralization properties. *Materials*, 13(5), 1096.